

ANALYZING MANDATORY REPORTING PRACTICES FOR HEPATITIS C VIRUS RNA TEST RESULTS IN THE UNITED STATES

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ABSTRACT

Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infection remains a significant public health concern in the United States (US), and timely reporting of HCV Ribonucleic Acid (RNA) test results is critical for surveillance and disease control. This study aimed to map the reporting requirements for HCV RNA test results across all US states. Data were collected from state health department websites, HCV case report forms, and HCV strategic plans. For states lacking publicly available information, we directly contacted HCV senior epidemiologists, surveillance managers, viral hepatitis prevention coordinators, and HCV nursing program coordinators via email and telephone. States were categorized based on their reporting requirements into three groups: (1) requiring both positive and negative HCV RNA test results, (2) requiring only positive results, and (3) requiring neither. The distribution of reporting requirements across the US was visualized using Map Chart. Findings reveal significant heterogeneity in HCV RNA reporting practices, highlighting gaps in standardized surveillance and opportunities for policy harmonization to enhance national HCV monitoring and intervention strategies.

KEYWORDS

Hepatitis C Virus, RNA Testing, Reporting Requirements, United States, Surveillance

Introduction

HCV: Hepatitis C Virus; RNA: Ribonucleic Acid; US: United States; CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention In this study, we collected information on the reporting requirements of HCV RNA test results for all states.

To determine the frequency and distribution of

reporting requirements of HCV RNA test results in the US, we used various sources. First, we examined state HCV reporting guidelines published on state department of public health websites as well as available HCV case report forms and HCV strategic plans. For states that we could not find web-based information on, we contacted state-based HCV senior epidemiologists, HCV surveillance managers, viral hepatitis prevention coordinators, or HCV nursing program coordinators via email or telephone. After obtaining information on the reporting requirements of HCV RNA test results from all states, we categorized each state into one of three categories: 1) Requires the reporting of positive and negative HCV RNA test results, 2) Requires the reporting of only positive HCV RNA test results, and 3) Does not require the reporting of either positive or negative HCV RNA test results.

Finally, we visualized the distribution of reporting requirements across the US using Map Chart (<https://www.mapchart.net/usa.html>).

Results

Figure 1 depicts the HCV RNA reporting requirements for all states. The proportion of states that require positive HCV RNA test results to be reported is ~98% (50/51). Idaho is the only state that does not require any HCV RNA

test results to be reported. The proportion of states that require negative, in addition to positive, HCV RNA test results to be reported is ~53% (27/51).

Discussion

It is encouraging to see that almost all US states require reporting of positive HCV RNA test results. However, only about half of the states require negative HCV RNA test results to be reported.

Some states that require only positive HCV RNA test results to be reported are planning to update regulations so that negative HCV RNA test results can be reportable. For example, Hawaii and Kansas are at this stage. We recommend that each state that does not require negative HCV RNA test results to be reported seek local technical assistance from state epidemiologists in the Council of State and Territorial Epidemiologists as soon as possible in order to update reporting requirements so that they are consistent with the CDC's recommendations.

Making negative HCV RNA test results reportable could help in planning better ways to meet the US's target of HCV elimination by 2030 [3]. Only three states (Connecticut, South Carolina, and Washington) are on track to achieve elimination by 2030 [4]. Without the required reporting of negative HCV RNA test results, the true number of active HCV infections is unknown. It is not possible to determine which people with a history of a positive HCV RNA test result have resolved their infection either spontaneously or with treatment. A more accurate number of infections can help states respond with interventions targeted to specific populations or geographic areas to get closer to HCV elimination. In addition, having negative HCV RNA test results reportable increases awareness regarding acute infections, both new and re-infections, and completeness of testing programs [2]. Even localities performing HCV case management, where public health staff contact reported cases regarding their positive RNA test result [5], benefit from the required reporting of negative HCV RNA test results. A negative HCV RNA test result, which identifies a case as treated or spontaneously cleared, saves public health staff time and resources from performing unnecessary case management. Finally, given the increasing incidence

of acute HCV cases that are related to the ongoing opioid epidemic [6] implementing the reporting of negative HCV RNA test results can help identify populations of people who inject drugs that are accessing treatment and not accessing treatment. Treating HCV in people who inject drugs is time-sensitive, as left untreated, one active injector can infect up to twenty others with HCV within the first three years of infection [7].

In summary, we have found that the required reporting of positive HCV RNA test results is widespread, but the required reporting of negative HCV RNA test results is lagging. For an accurate estimate of the prevalence and incidence of HCV in the US, both positive and negative HCV RNA test results should be reportable. In light of increased efforts toward the national elimination of HCV, an accurate estimate would be essential to inform public health planning and policy development.

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